

A PARALLEL STUDY OF MANDU AND DHAR
WITH AN URBAN APPROACH

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The twin cities of Mandu and Dhar situated at a distance of 35 Kilometers from each other present a complex and intricate relationship which calls for a parallel study of the two.¹ They present a picture of similarity and dissimilarity on one side and a complementary and inverse relationship on the other. A lot has already been written about the political and dynastic history of the two cities. Here, their inter-relationship with an urban approach has been examined.

The similarity of the two cities centres around three points. Firstly, both are basically medieval cities, having gained importance only in the medieval era of Indian history. Secondly, they come into existence and prominence roughly at the same time (i.e. in the 11th century) and lose significance at the same point and stage of history (i.e. with the advent of the Marathas). Thirdly, both have enjoyed the status of capital cities - Dhar being the capital of the Parmaras and Mandu those of Sultans of Malwa.

The dissimilarity between them is that they both served a different purpose and that is precisely why they could co-exist at the same time with a minor distance of 35 kilometers. Mandu, in the early medieval and Mughal times was a vantage point over looking the crossing of the Narmada and was on route to Burhanpur whereas Dhar was an important milestone on way to Gujarat. Tavernier travelled from Burhanpur to Mandu (Mandava)² and William Finch from Surat-Burhanpur and Mandu.³ Speaking of Dhar as a milestone on the route to Gujarat it is stated "at the end of every 12 'Yojanas' from Dhar to Anhilwara, stand horses ready littered, cannels can go a 'Yojana' in one Indian hour (24 minutes)."⁴

The relationship of the twin cities is complementary in the sense that both co-exist, lending support to each other. The relationship is inverse in the

sense that when one attains the status of the capital city, the other is reduced to the status of the capital and vice-versa - nevertheless giving support to the first. To be specific, when under the Parmaras "Dhar was the greatest cultural and literary centre of western Malwa⁵ and also their capital city, "The fortress of Mandu or Mandapadurga was raised by Bhoj and he established a college (university ?) which housed several hundred students.⁶ Mandapadurga was thus established by the Parmaras as a retiring resort in emergency since Dhar was easily accessible. The university could be a camouflage. On the other hand when Hoshang Shah shifted the capital of the independent kingdom of Malwa to Mandu and renamed it Shadiabad or city of joy,⁷ Dhar continued to be the city seat of Government or activity and he frequently visited Dhar.⁸

Origin, Nature and Growth of Dhar and Mandu :

There is hardly any reference to both the cities before the advent of the Parmaras when Malwa was under the imperial Guptas, the Pratiharas and the Rastrakutas. The Puranas and Buddhist sources refer to Ujjaini, Daspur and Mahismati⁹ but there is no reference to Mandu or Dhar before 1000 A.D. Dhar is mentioned as the 'Kularajadhani' or family seat of the Parmaras in the poetic work of Padmagupta. Varsimha II who recovered Malwa with the help of Rashtrakuta Krishna III is said to have established the capital at Dhar, having won it with the strength of his sword (Dhar = edge of the sword).¹⁰ Vindhayavarman (1215 A.D.) is said to be in possession of Dhar and Mandapadurga (note both always mentioned together) and Arjunavarmadava is said to have issued grants from Mandapadurga. In 1047 A.D. Somesvara I defeated Bhoja and sacked and burned Dhara and Captured Mandava.¹¹ Bhoja (1005-1055 A.D.) reoccupied Dhar and rebuilt it "putting into practice the principles of architecture that he enumerated in his treatises, the 'Samarangana Sutradhara' and 'Yuktikapataru'.¹² It can be contemplated that Budi Mandava (or the older Mandava situated at a distance of roughly 8 kilometers from the present one and now a deserted and inaccessible hillock) could have been the site of the early Mandu which was destroyed by Somesvara

and Mandava was the new site rebuilt by Bhoja. The 'Bhoj-Kunda', 'Somvati Kunda' at Mandav and 'Munj Sagar' behind Jahaj Mahal are testimony of Bhoja's presence at Mandu, which generally known as predominantly Muslim site.

Thus, under the 12 Kings of the Parmaras (who ruled from 1010 - 1250 AD giving an average of 20 years each) Dhar¹³ and Mandav both came into existence and prominence.

A lot of material is available about the glory of Dhar. It was a metropolitan town of beautiful palaces and pleasure gardens which were surrounded on the hills around it.¹⁴ Dhar was beautified with magnificent buildings.¹⁵ According to Bilhana¹⁶ and Cunningham¹⁷ the whole circuit of the palace was not less than 3½ miles. 'Parijata Manjari' corroborates that the city had 84 cross roads¹⁸ and the king's highway passed through it. The palace area of the city was clearly demarcated.¹⁹ Bhoj adorned his capital with architectural monuments.²⁰

Scholars from all over India came to attend the court of Dhar with a hope to receive rewards for their academic works.²¹ Merutunga and Ballala Pandit refer that Bhoj ordered "Let him who is a fool be outside my city even a Brahman. Let him (who is) wise remain in my city, even though a potter"²² Bhojashala was a university of all India importance.²³

Even the Muslim chroniclers extol the glory of Dhar. Alberuni refers to 10 routes of which four traversed Malwa through Dhar (1) Mathura-Dhar (2) Bajan-Dhar-Ujjain (3) Dhar to Mandagvi (4) Dhar-Tan (on the sea-coast)²⁴ Ibu Batuta writes "Jahar (Dhar) is the capital of Malwa²⁵ and that the distance of Delhi and Dhar is of 24 days"²⁶ Dhar was connected to Daulatabad, Nandurbar, Kambhat which are the cities of the Deccan.

Dhar and Mandu under the Muslims

Alauddin Khilji subdued Malwa "as far as Dhar"²⁷ The town of Mandu was captured by Ain-ul-mulk a general of Alauddin Khalji on 23 November 1305 AD. In 1305 AD Malik Kafur halted at Dhar on his return from Devgiri²⁸ and

"from 1304-05 AD the town of Dhar remained in a Mohammedan possession for over 500 years"²⁹ Barani refers to "the wealth of Deogiri being temporarily deposited at Dharagiri a strong fort (note) under Aziz³⁰ Himar." Muhammad Tughluq halted at Dhar in 1344 AD and found "the whole country desolated and that the posts were gone off the road."³¹ He saw "the outline of a fort very elegant and beautiful but the space inside empty of buildings".³²

This clearly shows that the town of Dhar built by the Paramaras was raised to the ground by the iconoclast Turks and that by 1344 AD most of the cities of Dhar and Mandu were desolate. The ruins of Budi Mandav, the defaced sculptures and images which scattered are available today and also lying under the magnificent buildings of Mandu are the relics of ancient Mandava garh.

Shadiabad - The City of Joy

Life again springs into Mandu under the Ghoris and the Khilji - Sultans of Malwa. It is rebuilt, reshaped and redeveloped as Shadiabad - A city of Joy; Asharfi Mahal, Jahaz Mahal, Jama Masjid, the Madarassa, the Karwan Sarai all bear testimony to this rebirth of the city.

Thus, it became the populous second Muslim city of Medieval India covering an area of a square miles.³³ The glory of Mandu is referred by Ali-bui-Mhd-Karmani Shahab-Hakim in 'Maasir-i-Mahmud-Shahi' by Mohammad, Bihimadkhan in 'Tarikh-i-Mohammadi'; by Ghias-uddin in 'Faraid-i-Ghiasi' Dilawar Khar fortified Mandu. Hoshang Shah had contact with Timur's son Shahrukh and had developed direct relations with Central Asia. The design and structure of Jama Masjid of Mandu proves that its architect was a widely travelled man. Many gifts were exchanged between Hoshang Shah and Shahrukh During the times of Mahmud Khilji I. Mandu became one of the important capital cities of India. "During the palmy days of the 15th century of the 12000 acres of the Mandu hill top, 5160 were fields, 370 were gardens, 200 were wells, 780 were lakes and ponds, 260 were baths, 470 were mosques, 334 were palaces, 100 were bazaar roads and 1500 were dwellings".³⁴

An anonymous work Tarikh-i-Muzzafari refers to the gala celebrations in Mandu on the occasion of Sultan Muzzfar Shah of Gujarat's visit to Mandu. The architecture of Chanderi and Mandu built by the same architect, left even Babur spell-bound.

Mandu was linked once again with Mandasaur, Sarangpur, Ujjain, Satwas, Chittor, Jodhpur, Agra. The Malvi-wheat and betal (pan) was sold in Delhi,³⁵ cloth sent to Turkey and Persia. the wine of Hasalpur (a village near Mandu) was famous.

Dhar-Mandu and the Mughals

Mahmud Khilji II was killed in 1531 AD by Bahadur Shah of Gujarat and Mandu became an annex of Gujarat Sultnate for a short while.³⁶ Sher Shah's Subedar Sujat Khan made Mandu his capital of Suba of Malwa and built a road from Agra-Burhanpur via Mandu. Akbar conquered Malwa in 1561 AD. Now Mandu was reduced to the status of a Sarkar in the Suba of Malwa. Abul Fazl refers to it "as a large city, 12 kms in circumference" (18 kos according to Ferishta). The Sarkar of Mandu had 16 Mahals, area 229, 969 Bighas, 15 Biswas and Revenue 13,788,994 dams.³⁷ Akbar appointed a Kanungo in Sarkar of Mandu, Anandtaram, his son Nandlal and Nilal are referred in Aurangzeb's time³⁸ Jahangir visited Mandu and stayed for seven months at Jahaz Mahal. It was just a resort.³⁹

With the advent of Marathas in Malwa Mandu and Dhar both lost importance by the 18th century. Instead of entering Malwa through Harida (Hadiya) the Marathas adopted the Barwaha ferry for crossing the Narmada. Thence, Mandu and Dhar were side tracked.

Population of Dhar and Mandu and

Migration Trends

Under the Parmaras though much has been written about the glory of Dhar and mandu there is total paucity of statistical data which could help us to reconstruct

the urban population of both the cities. Keeping in view the description about nature and expansion, Dhar could very well be a city with more than a lac of population comprising of various castes creeds and professions including teachers, engineers, architects, sculputures, garland makers, physicians, keepers of gambling house, barbers, hunters, butchers, jewel testesters, potters and sailors. Mandava had perhaps a sizable in proportion to the extent of the fort area. Dhara was crowded with people far it was situated in plain.⁴⁰ Till the end of 12th century, the population was basically Hindu - Saivas, Vaishans, Shaktas. The majority were Hindus, Jains were few and far between.⁴¹ The disturbances caused by the Turkish conquest of Ajmer (1193) resulted in a great influx of Jains in Mandu - mostly Digambars. The families of Pethad Kumar and Jhanjhan Kumar came and settled in Mandu and largely contributed to the development of Jain architecture of Mandapadurga.⁴² In 1258 A.D. Gujarat saw a rigorous famine during the reign of Visaladeva Vaghela and this also brought a steady stream of Swatembra Jain families claiming Rajput origin from Gujarat at the adjoining Malwa and Mandu.⁴³

During the Sultanate period, we witness a cross-migration of population from Delhi - Mandu, while, violent changes in Delhi resulted in the dispersal of many a moneyed families of Jains to the provincial capital. Mandu thus again witnessed an influx of Jain capitalists in Malwa. Between 1300-1313 A.D. many Brahmans had left Mandu for unknown destinations. May be, the advent of Muslims in Mandu in 1303 A.D. could be the factor responsible for this migration. With the Turkish conquest of Malwa in the early 14th century, the Muslim element entered Malwa. Turks, Afghans, Iranis-nobles Turranis settled down in the vicinity of Mandu.⁴⁴ Qazi Khan Badr Mohammad Dharwal was a Persian and patronised by Qddr Khan; Dildar Agacha, third wife of Babur was a Shia residing at Mandu. Arab Mongal merchants frequently came to mandu. The architectural remains of three caravan sarais in Mandu prove that it was an important centre of trade and commerce. Aulia Shah, Durgahi Mal, Darwesh, Shaikhu were Sufis of Chistia Silsila quite popular with the populace of Malwa.⁴⁵

The first statistical details of economic

significance of medieval period are furnished by Abul Fazl in his Ain. Which are described in the description of the Suba of Malwa. Various scholars like Moreland, Desai and Shireen Moosvi have calculated the population of India in the Mughal times on the basis of these records. Moreland fixes the population of Mughal India in 1601 AD at 6 million, Desai 64.9 million and Shireen Moosvi at 145 million.⁴⁶ The ratio of urban population to rural population has been fixed at 15:85. Applying the technique adopted by Moreland (i.e. to the number of armed retainers of the area apply a ratio of 1:30 for calculating the population of the area, we have arrived at a figure of 1,11,180 for the Sarkar of Mandu in Akbar's time.

Sarkar Mandu : Cavalry	1,180	
Infantry	2,526	
Total	3,706 x 30 = 1,11,180	population.

Shrieen Moosvi technique :⁴⁷

Gross area under cultivation

per capital land revenue which she has worked as 85.235 dams in Akbar's time

<u>13,788,994</u>	Revenue of Sarkar of Mandu
85,235	

1.11 brings us to the same figure. The population of the Sakar of Mandu and its 16 Mahals estimated around 1,11,080 in Akbar's time. Ain speaks of the "various castes" of the region.⁴⁸ Thus, by the end of 16th century Dhar and Mandu had lost their earlier predominantly Hindu character and a hetrogeneous population had evolved out.

With the downfall of the Mughal empire, Malwa became a plundering ground for the Marathas. The political turmoil and uncertainty in the region; the rivalry of the Holkars and Scindias; the advent of Pindaris in Central India: all had a telling effect on Malwa. Mandu and Dhar gradually lost their pre-eminence.

According to the 1971 census there were merely 1881 families living amongst the ruins of Mandu. The local population has increased to roughly 10,000; thanks to the expanding tourist activity. The residential expansion and the weekly market (hat) held in the vicinity of the Jama Masjid and the Madarasa is posing a threat to these monuments. Hope some action will be taken immediately to restore the sanctity of these monuments.

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